

ISSN:2814-063X

BASUG LAW JOURNAL

BASUG

LAW JOURNAL

Volume 2 | Issue 3
September, 2024

**A Publication of:
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University**

VOL. 2, ISSUE 3, 2024

**A Publication of:
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University**

BASUG

LAW JOURNAL

Volume 2, Issue 3, 2024

**Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University
2024**

BASUG Law Journal Volume 2 Issue 3 2024

Published by:

Faculty of Law,

Sa'adu Zungur University (formerly Bauchi State University)

For more information, see: www.basuglawjournal.com

To order:

Faculty of Law,

Bauchi State University, Gadau

No: 65, Kano-Kari Road,

Misau,

Bauchi State.

ISSN: 2814-063X

THIS JOURNAL SHOULD BE CITED AS BASUGLJ Volume 2 No 3 2024

The Bauchi State University, Gadau Law Journal welcomes contributions that advance legal scholarship and contribute to vibrant discourse within the legal community. We seek articles that demonstrate originality, depth, and relevance to contemporary legal issues.

EDITORIAL BOARD

1. Prof. SMG Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean,
Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University
2. Dr. Ibrahim Danjuma,
Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University
3. Prof. U. S. Abbo Jimeta,
Faculty of Law, University of Maiduguri
4. Prof. M. L. Yusufari, SAN
Faculty of Law, Bayero University, Kano
5. Prof. Jamila Nasir,
Faculty of Law, University of Jos
6. Prof. Shamsuddeen Magaji,
Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University
7. Assoc. Prof. Dr. Nuarrual Hilal MdDahlan,
School of Law, Universiti Utara Malaysia
8. Dr. Ahmed Salisu Garba
Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University
9. Dr. Mohd Zakhiri MdNor,
School of Law, Universiti Utara Malaysia
10. Dr. Abdulraheem Taofeeq Abolaji,
Faculty of Law, University of Ilorin, Kwara State
11. Dr. Garba Umaru Kwagyang,
Faculty of Law, University of Maiduguri
12. Dr. Sulaiman Santuraki
Faculty of Law, University of Maiduguri

EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

CONTENTS

Editorial Board_____	iv
Editorial Note_____	v
Articles	
An Assessment of the Medico-Legal and Ethical Issues in Surrogate Motherhood	
Agbo Friday Ojonugwa, Mary Arthur Jolasinmi, Grace Perpetual Dafiell_____	1
Examination of Islamic Takaful Insurance Model in Nigeria Vis-À-Vis the Powers of the National Insurance Commission (NAICOM)	
Ochenehi Dominic Sunday, Mohammed Bashir Saidu_____	19
Appraising The Jurisdiction of the Court and Competition and Consumer Protection Tribunal in Prosecuting Electricity Consumer Complaints in Nigeria	
Alfred M. Tijah, Kwaghkehe Ierkwagh_____	31
The Powers of the Central Bank of Nigeria On Currency Redesign: The Extend of Compliance with Law in 2023 Naira Redesign Policy	
Ibrahim Danjuma_____	53
An Analytical Review of the Constitutional Right to Life and Health	
Samuel UGBO, Omagbemi-Ariko Mercy Ebere_____	88
Health Response for Gender-Based Violence Survivors	
Adekilekun Medinat Adeola_____	109
Legal and Institutional Framework for The Establishment of the World Trade Organization (WTO): Trends, Challenges and Prospects for Nigeria	
Umar Abubakar Dubagari, Muhammad Waje Bawa_____	127
Environmental Non-Governmental Organisations and Their Status in Protecting the Environment	
Stella.O. Idehen_____	148
An Assessment of the inadequacies of personnel towards curbing Commercial Malpractices in Markets in Nigeria: Hisbah Institution as an option	
Ismail Danjuma Yusuf, Fatimah Tanimu Bindawa_____	164

Exploring Protections Available to Minority Members Under Nigerian Corporate Law

Shamsuddeen Magaji, Abubakar Garba Salisu _____ 183

One Man One Court: The Perils of Solitary Decision over Appeals at High Court

Lilian Ifeoma Nwabueze _____ 201

Recognising Corporate *Zakat* Under Nigerian Corporate Law as a Means of Alleviating Poverty in North-Eastern Nigeria

Shamsuddeen Magaji _____ 216

The Responsibilities and Sanctions of International Law During Armed Conflict: A Case Study of Russia and Ukraine War

Ibrahim Danjuma _____ 230

International Law and Diplomacy: Challenging The “Fixity” of State Sovereignty

Nelson E. Chegwe, Michael C. Ogwezzy _____ 254

Jurisdictional Issues and Choice of Law in E-Commerce in Nigeria

Amaayeneabasi Ini Enang _____ 271

Without Justice, Law Labours in Vain: A Critique of the Judgment of the Supreme Court of Nigeria in APC V. Bashr Sheriff & 3 Ors. (Lawan V. Machina)” SC/CV/1689/2022

Taiwo Olawoye Lawrence _____ 287

Comparative Study on the Enforceability of Contract of Restraint in Trade

Habila Isah Barau, Ibome Habila Bulmen _____ 318

Legal Implications and Limitations of the Executive Immunity clause in Nigeria

Ayub O. Mohammed _____ 336

The Utility of Wasiyya under Nigerian Contemporary Society

Alhaji Ahmed Rufai _____ 348

A Conceptual Discourse on Protecting the Rights of Electronic Commerce Consumers in Nigeria

Muhammad Nuruddeen _____ 356

AN ANALYTICAL REVIEW OF THE CONSTITUTIONAL RIGHT TO LIFE AND HEALTH

By

Samuel UGBO*, Omagbemi-Ariko Mercy Ebere**

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13855483

ABSTRACT

The rights to life and health are constitutionally provided for in some jurisdictions while in some others, only the right to life is constitutionally guaranteed as a fundamental right; the right to health is a provision of some international laws, treaties, instruments and enabling enactments. Consequently, the right to health is termed 'non-justiciable' in some climes and justiciable in other climes. The implication of this is that since the right to health is not justiciable, it cannot be enforced unlike the right to life which is a fundamental right and enshrined in the constitution. The objectives of this work include x-ray and juxtapose the right to life and health in some jurisdictions, and ascertain whether these rights are fundamental and justifiable. In carrying out this work, the doctrinal research methodology was adopted. This work found that both the right to life and right to health are germane, interdependent and interrelated, thus, both rights are interwoven as none of the rights can be taken from another. It is concluded that the right to health is an antidote and life wire of the right to life as no one can enjoy the right to life if he/she does not have good health. It is recommended amongst other things that the legislative arm of government in every country should as a matter of importance make the right to health and other socio-economic rights fundamental rights; that the courts must be bold to restore the sanctity of the judiciary as the last hope of the common man by ensuring that remedies must at all times be provided where there is right. It is hoped that the imbroglio relating to the justifiability of the right to health would be resolved if the recommendations are strictly adhered to by stakeholders and authorities.

Keywords: Right, Life, Health, Justiciable, Enforceability.

1. INTRODUCTION

The right to life and health is constitutionally guaranteed right in some countries like Nigeria¹. These rights are universally recognized and they are very important to every citizen of any country and across the globe. These rights are human rights – which represents, “demands or claims which individuals or group make on society, some of which are protected by law and have become part of *lex lata* while others remain aspirations to be attained in future”.²The right to life is the most recognized and important fundamental human right. This is sequel to the fact that without life an individual cannot enjoy other rights such as freedom of movement, association, dignity of his or her person, personal liberty, fair hearing, private and family life, freedom of thought, conscience, freedom of expression, peaceful assembly and association, freedom from discrimination, right to acquire property and so on. The fundamental rights as stated above are therefore, subjected to the right to life and even the good health of an individual. A man must be alive to enjoy the rights accorded to him by God Almighty, the constitution and international laws and instruments.

Again, the right to health has a correlation with the right to life. This is consequent upon the fact that for a man to have life he must first of all have good health. A bad health could lead to loss of life. It follows therefore, that citizens place very high demand on the need for good health. The government is responsible for the provision of good health by providing the basic necessities for her citizenry. Government at all levels has it as a responsibility to ensure the security of lives and property and welfare of its citizenry³; ensure that the health, safety and welfare of all persons in employment are safeguarded and not endangered or abused⁴; ensure that there are adequate medical and health facilities for all persons so they can be treated whenever they are ill. Also, the other fundamental rights mentioned earlier are rights given to humans in order to facilitate their good life. These rights which are inalienable help humans to prolong or keep their lives going. Human or fundamental rights are better parts of the right to life; of course, without these rights human life becomes short and brutish. It is submitted therefore, that both the right to life and health and other fundamental rights

*Ph.D, BL., ACARB; e-mail-samlegal2004@gmail.com, +2348080540346 University of Delta, Agbor, Delta State.

**Om agbemi-Ariko Mercy Ebere, LL.M, BL. (Ph.D in view), arikomercy11@gmail.com, +2348035452593.

¹See, ss. 33 and 17(1) (b)(c) and (d) CFRN 1999 (as Amended).

²O. Eze, *Human Rights in Africa: Selected problems* (Macmillan 1984) 5.

³S. 14(2)(b) CFRN 1999 (as Amended).

⁴*Ibid*, (2)(c).

are interdependent, interrelated and indivisible.⁵ This is akin to the fact that no right is independent or inferior to another. All rights are germane and very crucial to one another. It follows that the right to life, health, movement, association, speech, etc. are all related one way or the other and all such rights are important in the day to day management or running of the lives of individuals.

One problem encountered in carrying out this work is the issue of conflicting Court decisions as it borders the justiciability of the right to health. In some jurisdictions, the right to health is regarded as human rights whereas in other jurisdictions the right to health is construed as unjusticiable and socio-economic right as it is not embedded in the constitution as a fundamental right. This notwithstanding, this work was successfully carried out. The objectives of this work include to x-ray and juxtapose the right to life and health in some jurisdictions, and to ascertain whether these rights are fundamental and justiciable. In carrying out this work, the doctrinal research methodology was adopted.

It must be noted that the right to health has been institutionalized in so many international instruments such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1994, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights 1966 and the Convention on the Human Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2006, Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, the Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Racial Discrimination 1969, Convention on the Rights of the Child 1990, African Charter on Human and People's Rights and other relevant international laws and instruments made provisions to various rights including the rights to life and Health. All countries that are signatories to these international instruments are bound by their provisions.⁶

2. THE RIGHT TO LIFE

Life could be said to mean "a state of being alive as a human; an individual person's existence"⁷ Life itself is the immediate and the best gift of God to humans. It is part of natural gift by the Almighty God to man. The law of nature itself presupposes that since God Almighty the creator of every being gave life, no one no matter how highly placed

⁵A. K.A. Kolawole, 'The Right to Life and the Right to Health: Any Nexus?' (OIDA International Journal of Sustainable Development, vol. 2, No.52011).

⁶S. 12 CFRN (as Amended).

⁷B.A. Garner, Black's Law Dictionary, 11th edn (USA: Thomson Reuters, 2019) 1111.

he or she is should terminate the life of another for any reason except however, as excused by the laws of the land. Again, no government across the universe should tamper with the life of an individual except in accordance with the rule of law. The Holy Bible and the Q'uran forbid killing of human beings no matter the situation.⁸ This is premised on the fact that every human is equal and none is considered more important than another⁹ and also because life is sacrosanct and should not in any way be tampered with. In Nigeria, the right to life is a fundamental right enshrined in the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as Amended). It provides thus: “every person has a right to life, and no one shall be deprived intentionally of his life, save in execution of the sentence of a court in respect of a criminal offence of which he has been found guilty in Nigeria.”¹⁰

The constitution further provides that:

“a person shall not be regarded as having been deprived of his life in contravention of this section, if he dies as a result of the use, to such extent and in such circumstances as are permitted by law, of such force as is reasonably necessary” –

- a. for the defence of any person from unlawful violence or for the defence of property;
- b. in order to effect a lawful arrest or to prevent the escape of a person lawfully detained; or
- c. for the purpose of suppressing a riot, insurrection or mutiny.¹¹

A right is therefore, a legal or moral benefit of an individual which can be enforced. Rights could be social, civil, economic, political, cultural, or human. From the foregoing provision of the Constitution, it is crystal clear that killing is permitted by the law in certain circumstances. Also, the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights Ratification and Enforcement Act provides that “Human beings are inviolable; every human being shall be entitled to respect for his life and integrity of his person; no one may be arbitrarily deprived of this right”. The above provision emphasizes the importance of life and that life must at all times be preserved. In *Buddaycay v Secretary of State for the Home Department*¹², the importance of the right to life was

⁸Exodus 20:13; Quran 5:32.

⁹Y. Olom jobi, *Human Rights and Civil Liberties in Nigeria*, Revised edn (Princeton and Associates Publishing Co. 2018) 16.

¹⁰S. 33(1) CFRN 1999 (as Amended).

ii *ibid*, 33(2) a-c.

¹²(1987) I All ER. 940.

succinctly *re-enacted* when it was held that, “the most fundamental of all human rights is the individual’s right to life and when an administrative decision under challenge is said to be one which may put the applicant’s right to life at risk, the basis of the decision must surely call for the most anxious scrutiny”. Although it was stated earlier that all rights are interdependent and interrelated, it must however, be emphasized that the right to life is the most important of all the fundamental rights because without life, or the existence of an individual, he cannot possess a right. Therefore, there must be right to life first for other fundamental rights to exist. Therefore, the right to life refers to such right akin to a man’s humanity.¹³

Governments worldwide must endeavour to protect the life of their citizens in accordance with the provisions of the laws of the land. In *Bello v A.G. Oyo State*,¹⁴ an appeal existed before the execution of Bello. The Court frowned seriously at the attitude of the government of Oyo State, Nigeria describing such action as “reckless disregard for life and liberty of a subject and the rule of law.” It behooves of every nation to ensure that the life of its citizens must be protected from tyranny, fear and intimidation.¹⁵ Therefore, it is the responsibility of the government to protect the lives of its citizenry at all time. However, the question that comes to mind is whether the right to life is absolute. The constitution of Nigeria has provided that a person who dies as a result of the use, to an extent and in such circumstances as are permitted by law, of such force as is reasonably necessary, for the defence of any person from unlawful violence or for the defence of property; in order to effect a lawful arrest or to prevent the escape of a person lawfully detained; or for the purpose of suppressing a riot, insurrection or mutiny is permitted.

Again, a person’s right cannot be said to have been deprived intentionally where it involves the execution of the sentence of a Court in respect of a criminal offence which such a person has been found guilty in Nigeria. The above provisions of the constitution constitute exceptions to the right to life. In *Kalu v State*¹⁶, the Supreme Court of Nigeria stated that “death sentence is constitutionally valid”. It is however, submitted that the practice of death sentence is not the best policy as criminals might

¹³See, *Mustapha v Governor of Lagos State & Ors* (1987)2 NWLR (Pt. 58)539 at 585 cited in Y. Olomjobi, *Human Rights and Civil Liberties in Nigeria* Rev. edn (Nigeria Princeton & Association Publishing Co. 2018) 26.

¹⁴(1986)5 NWLR 828.

¹⁵See *Saidu v State*, (1987)2 NWLR (Pt. 58) 539 at 585.

¹⁶(1998) 13 NWLR (Pt. 583) 531.

have the tendency to change for good if they are reformed. The right to life is not absolute but qualified. Therefore, to execute a convict would not amount to trampling upon his/her right to life in Nigeria and other countries as it is enshrined in the constitution. This position of the law may be different in other jurisdictions.¹⁷ A person may not be held for murder if he or she uses reasonable means to defend or preserve his life.¹⁸

The right to life therefore, connotes freedom to live and choose a way of living and development. It is a cardinal point of the fundamental rights of the citizenry in any nation. The right to life is interdependent and interconnected with other fundamental rights as embedded in the constitution should not by any means or stroke of chance derogated from by any individual or government. It pursues happiness and this enhances the peoples' livelihood. The right to life clears the way for other rights to exist because where there is no life, other rights cannot exist or be enjoyed. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)¹⁹ tends to protect the rights of persons and provides for universal benchmark as it concerns human rights. The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR)²⁰ has its objectives to protect the rights of persons and hold states accountable for the violation of such rights. Again, the Convention Against Torture (CAT)²¹ condemns torture and other inhuman and degrading treatments meted at individuals. It tends to prevent and eradicate torture and other demeaning acts. The Banjul Charter was adopted in 1981 in Banjul, Gambia by the Organization of African Unity (OAU) now African Union A.U. The charter was adopted to promote human rights and the rule of law among other things in Africa. It recognizes the right to life.

3. THE RIGHT TO HEALTH

The preamble to the constitution of World Health Organization (WHO) as adopted at the International Health Conference, New York, 19-22 June, 1946 defines health as “a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity.” Health could be said to mean “the state of being free from illness

¹⁷See *State v Mekwanyane & Anor* (1995)6 B.C.L.R. 665.

¹⁸See *Musa v State* (1993)2 NWLR(Pt. 277) 550. See also, *Ali Zaman v The State* (2015) LPELR 24595. CA.

¹⁹Resolution 217 A (III) 1948 – 1949.

²⁰UN Treaty series vol. 99, NO. 14668, December 16, 1966.

²¹UN Treaty Series vol. 1465, NO. 24841, December 1987.

or injury”.²² It can also be referred to as ‘a person’s mental or physical condition’. The Black’s Law dictionary defines health as “the state of being sound or whole in body, mind, or soul; freedom from pain or sickness”. From the foregoing definitions, it can be deduced that health is all embracing as it concerns or affects the well-being of a person or citizen of a country. The right to health is an important and mandatory right desired by every individual in every society. It is the right of every citizen to have access to medical facilities and good health. This right is recognized locally and internationally. The constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), provides that “the health, safety and welfare of all persons in employment are safeguarded and not endangered or abused”.²³ It also provides that the state social order is founded on ideals of freedom, equality and justice; “there are adequate medical and health facilities for all persons”.²⁴ The right to health is a legal right, not a moral right. It includes right to good health care services, access to portable water, good food, shelter, environmental protection, etc. Thus, in *Odafe & Ors v A.G. Federation & Ors*,²⁵ the Court held that “the applicants who were prisoners deserve the right to the best standard of physical mental health”. It is the duty of the government in any country to provide medical treatment for those in prison.²⁶ Suspects who are detained in various security agencies’ cells and convicted criminals have right to good health while in the captive of the security agents and correctional centers (prisons). It is the responsibility of government or state to ensure that adequate healthcare facilities are provided for such prisoners or inmates.

4. THE RIGHT TO HEALTH, AN ECONOMIC OR CONSTITUTIONAL RIGHT?

The right to health is a universal recognized right in that series of international and regional organizations support the right to health. As stated earlier, like the right to life, the right to health is an all-important right as would be adumbrated later. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights,²⁷ International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights,²⁸ Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination

²²Oxford Language, Dictionary.

²³S. 17 (c) CFRN 1999 (as Amended).

²⁴*Ibid*, 17 (c).

²⁵(2004) AHRLR 205.

²⁶*Ubani v Director SSS* (1999) 11 NWLR (Pt. 129)

²⁷Article 25, 1948.

²⁸Article 12, 1966.

Against Women,²⁹ Convention on the Rights of a Child,³⁰ African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights,³¹ African Charter on Rights and Welfare of a Child,³² Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) Revised Treaty.³³ The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights,³⁴ an instrument for the protection of series of rights which encompasses right to life provides for "the right of everyone to the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health". The instrument acknowledges mental and physical health, meaning that good health is not limited to physical health alone but mental health too. The committee on Economic, Social and Cultural rights emphasized that health includes the underlying determinants of health and not just timely and appropriate health care. It therefore include good nutrition, food, housing, good employment and good environment, etc.³⁵ It remains the responsibility of the state to ensure that food, shelter, good environment, housing and other economic standards of life of the citizens are guaranteed. The International Covenant on Economic and Social Rights is not left out. It also provides for the right to health. The instrument states that states parties should ensure that steps are taken to achieve the full realization of the right to health in their various jurisdictions. States parties here, connotes member states who are signatories to such instrument.³⁶ The Universal Declaration of Human Rights equally made provisions to the effect that "everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family..."³⁷ It has been established that children should enjoy the highest attainable standard of health and the facilities for treatment of illnesses and rehabilitation of health facilities for the treatment of illnesses. States parties are advised to ensure that no child is deprived of his or her right to access to such health care services.³⁸ A cursory look at other instruments or Conventions such as the Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of

²⁹Article 12, 1979.

³⁰Article 24, 1989.

³¹Article 16, 1981.

³²Article 14, 1990.

³³Article 45, 1993.

³⁴This was adopted on 16 December, 1966, 993 U.N.T.S.3.

³⁵See, Y. Olom ojobi, *Medical & Health Law*, (Princeton & Associates Publishing Co. Ltd 2019) 5.

³⁶*Ibid*, Adopted on 16 December, 1996, 993 U.N. 153.

³⁷See, Art. 25 thereof.

³⁸Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, General Comment 12, The Right to the highest Attainable Standard of Health (UNDOCE/C12/200142000) cited in Y. Olom ojobi (supra).

Discriminations Against Women, Convention on the rights of persons with disabilities, International Labour Organization, and other instruments points to the fact that all persons are required to enjoy the highest attainable standard of health without any form of discrimination. What this implies is that, the instrument applies to everyone irrespective of his or her race, including children, women and the vulnerable, persons with disabilities, etc. All these instruments made provisions for the right to health and other fundamental rights.

Every human being requires a good health to be able to survive or live. Without good health, there would be no productivity in a nation. It is submitted that the right to health is both an economic and a fundamental right. The workforce in every nation must be provided with good healthcare delivery in order to deliver on their mandate.³⁹ Therefore, it behooves on a nation to prioritize her health care delivery system in order to provide and improve the health of her populace. The ill health of the citizenry would no doubt jeopardize the economic growth or prowess of a nation. A healthy nation is no doubt a wealthy nation, and as such, the good health of a people determines the strength of their workforce. And when the people are healthy enough, it encourages productivity in every strata or sphere of a country's socio-economic and political well-being. The right to life is the basic fundamental right of individuals. But the question that comes to mind is whether there would be life where there is poor health? Of course, poor health situation could lead to the death of an individual, and where there is no good health, death is the likely probable consequence. It follows therefore, that the right to health ought to and should be a fundamental right because good health itself is fundamental and the basic need of man. Nevertheless, as stated earlier, the right to health is a provision of the constitution of Nigeria. It provides that: the health, safety and welfare of all persons in employment are safeguarded and not endangered or abused; there are adequate medical and health facilities for all persons.⁴⁰ Unfortunately, this provision of the constitution is not embedded in the fundamental rights provisions in the constitution.⁴¹

Again, the constitution of Kenya made provisions to the effect that 'every person is entitled to the right to the highest attainable standard of health', encompassing such

³⁹*Ibid*, (n.1).

⁴⁰S. 17(1)(c) and (d) CFRN 1999 (as Amended).

⁴¹Chap. IV, ss. 33-46 CFRN 1999 (as Amended).

rights as health care services and reproductive healthcare system. Nonetheless, the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights also provides that "every individual shall have right to enjoy the best attainable state of physical and mental health, and that state parties to the charter shall take the necessary measures to protect the health of their people and to ensure that they receive medical attention when they are sick."⁴² The question again at this juncture is: "what does fundamental and economic rights refer to?"

Fundamental rights are constitutionally guaranteed rights which are inalienable.⁴³ They include rights to life, dignity of human person, personal liberty, fair hearing, private and family life, freedom of thought, conscience and religion, freedom of expression at the press, peaceful assembly and association, freedom of movement, freedom from discrimination, acquire and own immovable property, compulsory acquisition of property, etc.⁴⁴ The constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria provides that "any person who alleges that any of the provisions of the Chapter IV of the constitution has been, is being or likely to be contravened in any state in relation to him may apply to a High Court in that State for redress."⁴⁵ It must however, be noted that the right to health is not embedded in Chapter IV of the Nigerian constitution and this makes its enforcement as fundamental right somewhat cumbersome and elusive. However, the African Charter on Human and People's Rights made provisions for the right to health.⁴⁶ Nigeria is a signatory to such instrument and as such, its provisions are binding on Nigeria and Nigerians. Thus, in *Ogugu v State*,⁴⁷ the apex Court of Nigeria stated that "it is apparent that the Human and People's Rights of the African Charter on Human and People's rights are enforceable by the Courts depending on the circumstances of each case and in accordance with the rule and practices of each Court". It is submitted that the right to health ought to be ordinarily enforced under the African Charter on Human and People's Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act. The same position of the law was upheld in *Abacha & Ors v Gani Fawehinmi*,⁴⁸ where the Supreme Court of Nigeria held that, "any treaty enacted into law in Nigeria

⁴²Art. 16, African Charter on Human and People's Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act CAP. 10 LFN 2 004.

⁴³See *Uzokwu & Ors v Ezeonu 11 & Ors* (1991) 6 NWLR (Pt. 200) 708 @76.

⁴⁴*Ibid*, n. 25.

⁴⁵See, s. 46 CFRN 1999 (as Amended).

⁴⁶*Ibid*.

⁴⁷(1994) 9 NWLR (Pt. 366)1.

⁴⁸(2002) 6 NWLR (Pt. 600) 228.

by virtue of section 12(1) of the constitution is circumscribed in its operational scope and extant as may be prescribed by the legislature.” Again, the Apex Court was of the view that the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) is superior to the African Charter on Peoples’ and Human rights (Ratification and Enforcement), Act. This decision of the apex Court has therefore made the enforcement of the right to health nugatory. It is submitted that citizens can apply to enforce their fundamental rights to health under the African Charter on Human and People’s Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act, 1990. However, the enforcement and execution of the decisions of such regional Courts against the state are practically impossible. Fundamental rights are not absolute as they can be derogated from in the interest of defence, public safety, public order, public morality, public health or for the purpose of protecting the rights and freedom of other persons.⁴⁹ The Court is encouraged to proactively pursue enhanced access to justice for all classes of litigants especially the poor, illiterates, the uninformed, the vulnerable, the incarcerated and the unrepresented. The court shall equally encourage and welcome public interest litigations in the human rights field and no such human rights proceedings would be dismissed or struck out on the grounds of *locus standi*.⁵⁰ It follows that where there is right, there is remedy – *ubi jus ibi remedium*, and an organization can file a case in court on behalf of a people who cannot afford to litigate on issues of human right. On its part, Economic Rights or socio-economic rights are rights aimed at ensuring that citizens of a country can access the resources and every opportunity which are of necessity to live a life. It encompasses such rights which would keep a citizen going and the need for the citizens to be carried along in the scheme of things. They are such very important rights for the general well-being of the citizenry. Some of these rights include but not limited to right to health, right to minimum wage, right to employment and social benefits, right to education, good and healthy work environment, protection from forced labour and human trafficking, etc. Chapter II of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as Amended) made provisions for the fundamental objectives and directive principles of state policy. The said constitution enjoins all organs of government, and of all authorities and persons, exercising legislative, executive or judicial powers, to conform to, observe and apply the provisions of

⁴⁹See, *Mrs Yetunde Ogunbesan & Ors v Hon. Minister of Health & Social Services* (1995) FHCLR 168.

⁵⁰See, the Preamble to the Fundamental Rights (Enforcement procedure) Rules 2009.

Chapter II of the constitution.⁵¹ It provided that sovereignty belongs to the people;⁵² the security and welfare of the people shall be the primary purpose of government. It equally embedded Federal Character in the constitution.⁵³ It also provided that the state shall direct its policy towards ensuring:

- a. the promotion of a planned and balanced economic development;
- b. that material resources of the nation are harnessed and distributed as best as possible to serve the common good;
- c. that the economic system is not operated in such a manner as to permit the concentration of wealth or the means of production and exchange in the hands of few individuals or of a group; and
- d. that suitable and adequate shelter, right to food and food security, reasonable national minimum living wage, old age care and pensions, and unemployment, sick benefits and welfare of the disable are provided for all citizens.⁵⁴

The chapter also provides for adequate health, safety and welfare of all persons; adequate medical and health facilities for all persons.⁵⁵ These rights as embedded in Chapter II of the Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended), do not seem to constitute fundamental rights as contained in chapter IV of the constitution. This is sequel to the fact that there are no provisions as to how they can be enforced unlike the fundamental rights. In a nutshell, they cannot be enforced even if the Courts gives orders as to their enforcement because they are not justiciable, so to say. The question that comes to mind is why are these rights not enshrined in Chapter IV of the constitution? However, some of these rights are provided for in the African Charter on Human and People's Rights and other regional and international laws, treaties and instruments mentioned earlier in this work, as justiciable rights. Therefore, such rights can be enforced under such regional and international instruments. Thus, in *African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights (African Commission) in Social and Economic Rights Action (SERAC) & Anor v Nigeria*,⁵⁶ the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) Court stated that the

⁵¹S. 13 CFRN 1999 (as Amended).

⁵²S. 14 (1).

⁵³*Ibid*, S. 14(3) CFRN.

⁵⁴S. 16(1).

⁵⁵S. 17(1).

⁵⁶AHRLR 60(2001).

directive principles of state policy of the Federal Republic of Nigeria are not justiciable before the Court and held that the provisions under directive principles of state policy were justiciable but under the exclusive jurisdiction of the Federal High Court of Nigeria. The Court further stated that the right to education which the plaintiff complained of is embedded in Article 17 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights is independent of the right to education under the directive principles of state policy as enshrined in chapter II of the constitution of Nigeria. It was however, held in *Registered Trustees of the Socio-Economic Rights and Accountability Project (SERAP) v The Federal Republic of Nigeria & the Universal Basic Education Commission*,⁵⁷ that all Nigerians enjoy the right to education. All organs of government must conform to, observe and apply the provisions of the constitution, most especially under chapter II as it concerns fundamental objectives and directive principles of state policy.⁵⁸

In South Africa, socio-economic rights such as the right to health, education, food, shelter, civil and political rights are justiciable. Thus, in *Republic of South Africa v Grootboom*,⁵⁹ it was held that the South African Constitution entrenches both civil and political rights and social economic rights. All these rights are interrelated and mutually supporting. The Court further held that there can be no doubt that human dignity, freedom and equality are the values of the society and when people are denied the right to food, clothing, shelter, as enshrined in the bill of rights, the fundamental rights have been breached. The interconnectedness of these rights needs to be taken into account in considering or interpreting the socio-economic rights. Also, in *Soobramoney v Minister of Health*,⁶⁰ the issue before the South African Constitutional Court was the obligation to create an enabling environment for the citizens to have access to healthcare services and treatments on emergency. It was held that it is the obligation of the state to so provide. Just as it was also held that the state is under obligation to ensure that cancer patients have adequate provision for the treatment of cancer.⁶¹

⁵⁷Suit No: ECW/CCJ/APP/12/07.

⁵⁸See *Organ v Nigeria Liquefied Natural Gas Ltd* (2012) All FWLR (Pt. 535) 293.

⁵⁹(2001) 36 WRN 137 at 162.

⁶⁰SA 765 (cc).

⁶¹See, *Nzimandev Minister Health* (2014) (6) S. A. 50544761/2013. Also, in *Khosa v Minister of Social Development* (2004), the Court held that vulnerable citizens must be provided with healthcare and social assistance. The realization of the right to health especially to the weak and poor in South Africa is the key mandate in the sector.

In India, the situation is not different. Thus, the Court held in *Francis Coralie v Union Territory of India*,⁶² that:

The right to life include the right to live with human dignity and all that goes with it, namely the bare necessities of life such as adequate nutrition, clothing and shelter, the magnitude and components of this right would depend upon the extent of economic development of the country, but it must, in any view of the matter, include the bare necessities of life... The fundamental right to life, which is the most precious human right, must be interpreted in a broad and expansive spirit so as to invest it with significance and vitality which may endure for years to come and enhance the dignity of the individual and the worth of the human person, we think that the right to life include the right to live with dignity and all that goes with it, namely the bare necessities of life such as adequate nutrition, clothing and shelter.

5. INTERPRETATIONS BY THE COURTS IN SOME JURISDICTIONS

In Kenya, the Supreme Court has held that the state has a duty to provide parameters and measures towards ensuring that socio-economic and cultural rights are preserved. The Court recognized socio-economic and cultural rights as such rights which cannot be transferred to another as they are also God-given rights. Over 3,000 households were evicted from their place of abode despite a Court order. The High Court held for the community but, the decision was overturned by the Court of Appeal. The Supreme Court later dismissed the Court of Appeal judgment and upheld the decision of the High Court.⁶³

In *J.M. v A.G. & Ors*,⁶⁴ it was held that the government has it as an obligation to ensure that every child in Kenya has basic education and that it must be free and mandatory. The government was equally ordered to ensure that this right is realized at all times. Again, in Nigeria, the Supreme Court in *Attorney General, Ondo State v A.G of the Federation*,⁶⁵ clarified the non-justiciability of Chapter II of the Constitution of Nigeria when the apex Court stated that it would amount to a deficiency of obligation on the state, and branches of government, if they acted in contempt of the fundamental

Thus, socio-economic rights are very crucial and the Courts have always propagated such rights in the above cases in South Africa.

⁶²AIR 1978 SC @ 746.

⁶³Petition No. 3 of 2018 (decision delivered on 11 January 2021).

⁶⁴(2021) eKLR.

⁶⁵(2002)9 NWLR (Pt. 772) 222.

objectives and the directive principles of state policy. It is noted that human rights are better protected if they attract binding force and enforceability.⁶⁶

A fortiori, the right to life and the right to health are interdependent as both rights function hand in hand. The criticism against the right to health is the absence of its enforceability which makes its propagation weak. It becomes very difficult therefore, to compel duties as it affects the right to health.⁶⁷ For a citizen to be able to preserve the enjoyment of his fundamental rights, he must first and foremost possess a good health. A person should be alive and healthy in the first place before thinking about the enforcement of his right. It follows that there must be remedy for the breach of any right including the right to health. Again, it behoves on the state to strive and endeavour to protect the rights of her citizenry at all times by ensuring that her citizens possess good health, shelter, food and good nutrition etc. It is incumbent upon the government to ensure that these rights whether fundamental or socio-economic, are protected to enthrone growth, stability and national development in the system. In *Paschim Banga Khet Mazdoor Sanity v State of West Bengal*⁶⁸, the Indian Supreme Court held that by virtue of the Indian Constitution⁶⁹ which borders on the right to life, no patient on emergency should be denied medical treatment or attention either as a result of inadequate medical facilities or lack of bed space. The apex Court of India stated that it is the responsibility of the state to provide some facilities irrespective of their financial status. What this implies is that it does not matter whether the state is financially constrained or not but what matters is the health of the citizens is very crucial and must be taken seriously, not to be treated with levity. Also, in *Purohit and More v The Gambia Communication*,⁷⁰ it was held that the right to respect for human dignity, liberty, fair hearing must be upheld.

Cultural rights are socio-economic rights as enshrined in International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR)⁷¹. People are allowed to choose their cultural identity. This right is a free one and no one should be compelled to do so as it heralds cultural diversity. Different people have different cultural values and

⁶⁶Z. Nampewo, J.H. Mike and J. Wolff, 'Respecting, Protecting and Fulfilling the Human Right to Health' (International Journal for Equity in Health 2136, 2022) <https://doi.org/10.1186/>.

⁶⁷*Ibid.*

⁶⁸(1999) SOL Case No 169 (S.C.).

⁶⁹Art. 21.

⁷⁰241/2001 (2003) AHRLR96 (ACHPR 2003).

⁷¹See, Art. 15(1)(a)1966.

backgrounds and this would no doubt bring about unity in diversity. However, someone's cultural practice should not be a yardstick for the breach or trampling upon another's right. Culture differs and it is dynamic in nature, so, every culture and values are subject to changes from time to time. It is the right of a people to possess a particular culture and values. Culture is simply the way of life of a particular people living in a particular location. It is their right to possess such culture and the people must not be undermined for having a way of life except such culture is barbaric and contravenes the constitution.

It has been pointed out that:

All civil, cultural, economic, political and social human rights are of equal value and dependent on each other for their mutual realization. There are two International Covenants on Human Rights because of the more complex nature of economic, social and cultural rights which needed particularly careful drafting and mechanisms of implementation adjusted to their specific nature... the suggestion that economic, social and cultural rights are not justiciable was never accepted in the course of the elaboration of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural rights.⁷²

In Australia, the right to health could be said to be socio-economic right, not a fundamental right. However, Australia has ratified series of international treaties on the right to health. The Constitution of Australia did not provide for the right to health. This notwithstanding, there are other enabling enactments and policies that guide the right to health in Australia. These enactments include: Australian Health Care Agreements; National Health Act of 1953; Medicare Act of 1983; Private Health Insurance Act 2007, etc. These enactments and other health policies are provided to pave way for access to healthcare delivery in Australia. This is the position in so many countries worldwide. This has made the enforcement and implementation of these rights cumbersome as they are not encapsulated in some countries' constitutions. For such rights to be enforced and pursued vigorously, it is better enshrined in the constitution especially in the Bill of Rights or fundamental rights as it is known in some countries. However, the Courts have interpreted these rights to be constitutional. In *Ashgar Leghari v Federation of Pakistan*,⁷³ the Court held that the state's delay and

⁷²Human Rights in the Administration of Justice, Chap. 14: The Role of the Courts in Protecting Economic, Social and Cultural Rights.

⁷³W.P. No. 25501/2015.

lethargy in implementing the framework offends the fundamental rights of citizens that need to be safeguarded. The Court further found that within the Pakistan legal and constitutional context, climate change is a “Clarion call for protection of fundamental rights of the citizens of that country, and to protect those that cannot approach the Court to seek redress. Again, in *Taskin & Ors v Turkey*⁷⁴, the European Court of Human Rights stated that environmental pollution could offend the European Convention on Human Rights – right to private and family life.⁷⁵ The Court held the Turkish government to have violated the rights of the citizens irrespective of the fact that such pollution did not amount to positive health related aftermath.

In the United States of America (USA), the Court has stated that abortion is not a constitutionally guaranteed right neither is it a fundamental right. This decision has no doubt restricted abortion and it gave rise to the dormancy and restriction of abortion laws in the U.S.⁷⁶ This Court decision also overturned the decision in *Roe v Wade*⁷⁷ and *Planned Parenthood v Casey*,⁷⁸ in which the Supreme Court of the U.S. held that individuals had the right to abortion. And in *Grisworld v Connecticut*,⁷⁹ the Supreme Court of the U.S. held that taking inference from the amendments in the Bill of Rights, it is obvious that the rights would not enable states to make the use of contraception by married couples illegal.

The table below shows some countries where the right to health is justiciable and upheld by the Courts and others where the right to health is not justiciable and refused by the Courts.

S/N	Countries Where Right to Health is Justiciable	Countries Where Right to Health is not Justiciable
1.	Australia	Argentina
2.	Canada	Brazil

⁷⁴App. No. 46117/99 Eur. Ct. H. R(2004)(2006)42 EHRR50.

⁷⁵Art. 8 thereof.

⁷⁶See, *Dobbs v Jackson Women’s Health Organization* No. 19 -1392 597 U.S. 215 (2022).

⁷⁷410 U.S. 113.

⁷⁸505 U.S. 833.

⁷⁹381 U.S. 479 (1965).

3.	China	Ecuador
4.	Germany	India
5.	Russia	Kenya
6.	Saudi Arabia	Philippines
7.	United States of America	South Africa
8.		Uganda
9.		Nigeria

Note however, that the list of the countries in the table above are not exhaustive and that countries across the globe may from time to time amend their various constitutions to either accommodate or remove such right from their constitutions. In some countries too, the Courts have been bold enough to pronounce that the right to health is constitutional despite the fact that its implementation and execution is illusory.

From the plethora of decided cases on socio-economic rights above, it is deducible that the fundamental rights in various countries are enshrined and embedded in various states constitutions and enforcement procedures embedded in the constitutions and other enactments.⁸⁰ These rights are equally embedded in so many international treaties which even if some countries are signatories to such international treaties, instruments and charters, their enforcement by the international or regional organizations may not be easy thereby rendering such treaties nugatory and impotent. Again, socio-economic rights in most countries are not contained in their constitutions. They are provided for in some enabling laws and function as a matter of policy. This does not augur well with the people because the weak and the most vulnerable who are susceptible to these challenges would suffer the non-implementation and enforcement of these rights. This notwithstanding, the Courts being the arbiter and the last hope of the ordinary man and the vulnerable should at all times when called upon to do justice to human rights issues, endeavour to uphold the dignity and sanctity of the rule of law and ensure that justice must not only be done but must be seen to have been done, and that wherever there is right, there should be

⁸⁰See, for example, s.46 CFRN 1999 (as Amended) and s. 3, the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 Fundamental Rights Enforcement Procedure) Rules, 2009.

remedy – *ubi jus ibi remedium*. It has however, been observed that socio-economic rights are similar to both civil and political rights. Thus, it is argued that:

The social and economic rights guaranteed by the European social charter are intrinsically linked with the civil and political rights enshrined in the European Convention on Human Rights. In Europe today, there is an urgent need not only to underline the importance of these rights but, above all, to avoid a narrow approach under which only some are seen as human rights... how can political rights be exercised without effective access to health? That is the whole point of the work of the European Committee of Social Rights, which Supervises Council of Europe member states' respect for social and economic rights.⁸¹

From the foregoing, it is quite understood that socio-economic rights such as rights to health, education, social security, right to living wage, right to food, water, family, housing and other needs of humans or citizens are associated with the fundamental and political rights as enshrined in the constitutions, various charters, instruments and other enactments. These rights interfere with one another and they are interdependent and interrelated to one another. A person who is not healthy enough cannot be thinking of exercising his or her right to franchise neither can he or she complain of his fundamental right to freedom of movement and association, etc. This notwithstanding, the rights to life and health are very germane and are necessary for human existentiality, thus, should not be derogated from by both humans and the states.

6. CONCLUSION

This work has examined the right to life and health and the attitude of the Courts toward the contravention of these rights by the states in some jurisdictions. It found that most countries have the right to life embedded in their various constitutions while the right to health is enshrined in some enactments by the legislatures. The right to life and health is also embedded in so many international treaties and instruments. Countries that are signatories to these treaties and instruments adhere to the provisions of such treaties. However, these rights, (right to life and health) are

⁸¹G. Palmisano, 'Social Economic Rights are also Fundamental Rights' https://www.coe.int/en/web/human-rights-rule-of-law/2015-news/-/asset_publisher/8oxoWVBBC6ohe/content/social-and-economic-rights-are-also-fundamental-rights, accessed 28 May, 2024.

interdependent and they interwove as they relate to each other. This is so because for a person to possess right to life admits that the person possesses good health. And good health is an integral part of life. Life itself cannot be achieved without good health. This is the interrelation and the interdependency that is being discussed. It follows therefore, that this discourse cannot be said to have been thoroughly dealt with, without emphasizing the importance of health or good health to life. A man has to live in order to enjoy his fundamental rights. One fundamental right is as important as another. This is the interdependence, interconnection and interrelation that exist between various rights including socio-political and economic rights.

In conclusion, it must be noted that the enforcement of socio-economic rights such as the right to health and education may pose some burden or challenges as many of such rights are not embedded in the constitution of some countries, and even if it is enshrined in the constitution, the implementation or execution of Court judgments and orders against the state have not been an easy task, and this somewhat makes the implementation or scenario illusory. Overall, it must be noted that the right to health is such an important right which if derogated from would thwart the realization and actualization of other rights such as right to life, education, movement, political rights, etc. Where there is good healthcare, and the people are healthy or have access to good healthcare, they would be able to pursue other rights, and development strides that would strengthen and improve the development of a nation. Finally, socio-economic rights are as important as fundamental rights. It follows that such rights should not be treated with any form of equivocation or levity but it should be handled and managed with every sense of seriousness and priority. The right to health and other socio-economic rights are therefore, fundamental in their nature like every other right.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The legislative arm of government in Nigeria and other countries that hold the right to health and other social-economic rights as unjusticiable must ensure that legislations to protect the enforcement of socio-economic rights are enacted. Therefore, fundamental objectives and directive principles of state policy embedded in Chapter II of the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999, (as amended) should be made fundamental rights and enshrined in the constitution with the provision for its enforcement mechanisms.

2. Also, the legislature must ensure that adequate resources are appropriated to the health sector in order to enhance socio-economic rights such as right to have access to healthcare delivery and other such rights.
3. Sanctions should be imposed on countries or states that do not obey court orders on the fundamental and socio-economic rights as enshrined in the constitution, treaties and other enactments or policies in every state.
4. The judiciary must be upright and should endeavour to uphold its dignity and sanctity in adjudicating on matters bordering on rights whether fundamental or socio-economic rights.
5. The executive and legislative arms of government must as a matter of importance ensure the propagation of these rights in order to promote the economic growth of their various countries.
6. Institutions saddled with the responsibilities of enforcing fundamental and socio-economic rights should endeavour to carry out such responsibilities diligently without fear or favour.
7. The Courts must be able to do justice at all times and ensure that where there is right there must be remedy – *Ubi jus ibi remedium*, no matter whose ox is gored.